

Sensitive Data Toolkit for Researchers

Part 3: Research Data Management Language for Informed Consent

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13th May 2026

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Alliance** of Canada

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Introduction

This tool, *Research Data Management Language for Informed Consent*, is intended to assist researchers interested in data sharing or deposit to develop tailored, deposit-friendly language for ethics approval and informed consent. In the case of deposit for future unspecified uses, the applicable guidance is related to broad consent, which is described under Article 3.12 of the [Tri-Council Policy Statement on Ethical Conduct for Research Involving Humans](#). The key principle of this tool is **Adaptation, Not Adoption**, meaning this is intended as guidance that will have to be tailored to your context and research project. Please see [chapter 9 of TCPS2](#) for distinction-based considerations with respect to research involving Indigenous peoples.

Sample text is provided to address a number of informed consent considerations, including:

- Scope of Data Use
- Anonymity and Confidentiality
- Data Storage and Access
- Limitations to Data Withdrawal
- Future Use of Data and potential for linkage
- Signature Acknowledgements

Note that many institutional REBs have their own informed consent documentation, templated language, and sample forms. **Consult your REB if you would like to deviate from institutionally provided guidance.** As with other guidance, what is presented here does not override any legal, regulatory or policy requirements of your institution or jurisdiction.

Please consult Part 1 of this toolkit, the [Glossary of Terms for Sensitive Data used for Research Purposes](#), for key definitions. Please consult Part 2 of this toolkit, the [Human Participant Research Data Risk Matrix](#), to determine the risk level of your data.

This tool has been informed by an environmental scan of secondary use of data policies, procedures, and forms at: Mount Saint Vincent University, Harvard University, University of Toronto, The Hospital for Sick Children, Brock University, Utrecht University, and Queen's University.

This tool is an updated version of a similar tool originally prepared by the Portage Network's Sensitive Data Expert Group, composed of a broad membership from research communities - including research ethics professionals, representatives of funding agencies, and members

of Indigenous organizations - with direct interests in sensitive research data. The group worked together to develop practical guidance and tools for managing sensitive data in the Canadian landscape.

Research Data Management Language for Informed Consent

Note: Consent for data storage and reuse should be separate from consent to participate in the named research project.

Scope of Data Use

The [Human Participant Research Data Risk Matrix](#), helps researchers determine risk level for human participant research data (taking into consideration sensitivity, identifiability and downstream risks), and make decisions with respect to its management, deposit, and appropriate access/future use. Researchers should be specific about the scope of possible uses and mechanisms by which data may be obtained by persons outside of the research team (if applicable) in their consent language. Researchers should also reference relevant institutional guidelines and requirements in decision-making. Data uses are categorized as:

- **Defined Use** - Data use will be limited to the specific project under consideration;
- **Broad Use** - Data must have a restriction on its reuse, for example, new projects that are in the same general area of research (e.g. breast cancer, diabetes, childhood trauma, poverty).

Note that Broad Consent is distinct from unrestricted or [Blanket Consent](#). Under the TCPS2 Broad consent is permitted but Blanket consent is not. Broad consent under TCPS2 also requires clarity on governance procedures, so whatever researchers do has to be aligned with what was in the original consent on adjudication of future uses. Contact your REB if you are not sure what sort of reuse is applicable to your project.

*Refer to the [Human Participant Research Data Risk Matrix](#) - the level of data risk can help inform the language that researchers use in informed consent forms.

Anonymity and Confidentiality

Only research that does not involve the collection of any direct and/or indirect identifiers that can be reasonably traced to individual respondents can be called anonymous. Under TCPS2 researchers working with identifiable data have obligations to protect participants' privacy, and safeguard the confidentiality of their data. Furthermore, researchers must also comply with applicable privacy related legal and regulatory requirements. See the [glossary definitions](#) for further information.

Researchers are strongly encouraged to carefully consider, select, and adapt language in this section to suit the specific needs of their research.

- This study involves collection of anonymous data. This means that no identifying information will be collected, including your name or contact information, and that you cannot be identified from the data.
- This study involves collection of identifying information. The research team will protect your identifiable data, including your name, so that no one will be able to connect your responses with any other information that identifies you. They will separate your name from your information as soon as possible, using instead an assigned number or code to match your study record with your answers.
- Federal or provincial laws or regulations, or university policy may require the researcher to show information to the university, government officials, sponsors, or the REB who are responsible for monitoring the safety and integrity of this study. All identifying information will be removed or modified before any data are shared. Any information provided to the public will be in aggregated form only.
- You will not be identified in any publication from this study.

Data Storage and Access

Participants need to be informed about and consent to which data (e.g., their data in anonymized form) will be stored or made accessible for discovery and access. Decisions about how long data will be accessible in a given repository, and/or preserved for long-term access, may involve consideration of repository terms of use, university and funder policies and other factors. Researchers are encouraged to contact relevant institutional support units for more information, if needed.

Researchers are strongly encouraged to carefully consider, select, and adapt language in this section to suit the specific needs of their research.

- During the study, information from this research will only be accessed by the research staff. All identifying information collected about you will be destroyed once it is no longer needed for the study.
- The principal investigator will keep a link that identifies you to your coded information, but this link will be kept secure and available only to the principal investigator and/or selected members of the research team. Any information that can identify you will remain confidential.
- At the end of the project, the principal investigator will irrevocably strip the data of direct identifiers, a code will not be kept to allow future re-linkage, and the risk of re-identification of individuals from remaining indirect identifiers will be very low.
- Anonymized data will be retained indefinitely to support research transparency, reproducibility, and future reuse for new research projects within the same field of study. Please note that anonymized data may be made available online in a

repository accessible to researchers around the world. This is common practice in research and required by many journals and funders.

Limitations to data withdrawal

While research participants must always have the right to withdraw participation from a study, the ability to withdraw their data is not absolute. Participants should be informed about their right to withdraw from a study, how to make such a request, how this will affect the data collected about them, and any limitations that may exist to fulfilling such a request. Generally speaking, participants need to be informed as to which of the following options is applicable to their data in a given study:

- They cannot withdraw their data (e.g., data are either anonymous, or identifiers have been irrevocably stripped)
- They can withdraw their data with limitations (e.g., by a certain date)
- They can withdraw their data without limitation

Researchers are strongly encouraged to carefully consider, select, and adapt language in this section to suit the specific needs of their research.

- Research study participants may choose to no longer take part in the study at any time, however participant data may only be withdrawn up to and including _[insert date]_____, at which time _[describe action]_____ (e.g. identification will have been stripped and we will no longer be able to remove your data; data will be anonymized; etc.)
- If you withdraw from the study, you do not have to state why. Please inform the researcher about your decision. All data already collected from or about you up until that moment will be used for the current research.
- You may withdraw from this optional study at any time without giving reasons. If you choose to enter the study and then decide to withdraw at a later time, you have the right to request the withdrawal of your information [and/or samples] collected during the study. This request will be respected to the extent possible. Please note however that there may be exceptions where the data [and/or samples] will not be able to be withdrawn -- for example, where the data [and/or sample] are no longer identifiable (meaning they cannot be linked in any way back to your identity) or where the data have been merged with other data.
- If you would like to request the withdrawal of any of your data [and/or samples], please let the researcher know.

Future Use of Data

Where possible, participants should be informed about future use of their data, including which data would be stored and made available, the scope of potential future use, as well as any specific limitations. Please note that data repositories have different requirements when it comes to future access to data. Ensure participants are informed of applicable information as set out in [Chapter 3.13 of TCPS2](#), including whether:

1. Data will only be accessible to projects with REB approval
2. Data will only be accessible according to the terms of a data access agreement

Researchers are strongly encouraged to carefully consider, select, and adapt language in this section to suit the specific needs of their research while protecting research participants. Please consult the [Human Participant Research Data Risk Matrix](#) in determining which level of access is appropriate.

- The data (personal information, biological samples, responses, etc.) you provide for this research study will be stored and may be used
 - in this research study only.
 - in future related research studies.
 - in future related research areas.

Prior to storage and future use, any identifying information will be removed from the data, and information/samples will not be linked back to you. Once this is completed, we will no longer be able to identify your specific data.

- Researchers outside of this specific study may request access to the collected dataset/samples for new research purposes. You will not be asked to provide additional informed consent for the use of your anonymous/anonymized data/samples for future research.
- Other researchers may request access to de-identified data in the future and may plan to link these data with other data which may render participants potentially identifiable. Access will only be granted if they agree to preserve the confidentiality of the information as requested in this form. If you have any questions about this, contact the Principal Investigator.
- Your decision to allow your information to be in the database is completely voluntary. While there may be no benefit to you, your information will help researchers to quickly identify individuals who may be suitable for a new research study. If you change your mind after agreeing to this, your information can be removed from the database. You will not be penalized in any way if you refuse to participate, or if you change your mind and ask that your information be removed.

- Your personal information and/or biological samples collected during this study will not be used or distributed for future research studies even if the information is anonymized and cannot be linked back to you.

Signature Acknowledgements

At the end of the consent form, participants may be provided with a brief statement summarizing what they are agreeing to. Participants should not be restricted from participating in research if they opt not to allow the research team to share their data.

Researchers are strongly encouraged to carefully consider, select, and adapt language in this section to suit the specific needs of their research.

- I agree that research data gathered for the study may be deposited, published, or made available provided my name or other identifying information are not used.
- I understand that the research data, without any personal information that could identify me (not linked to me) may be shared with others.
- I agree that use of my research data/samples will be limited to my anonymized data only.
- I understand that my anonymized data may be placed into a research data repository ([name and details of repository, such as terms or governance, if known, restrictions on re-use, etc.]).
- In addition to the use of my data as described above, I further agree to the following use of my data:
 - **Broad Use (example #1)** - Anonymized data may be used in future research projects that are either an extension of the original project or that are in the same general field of research (for example, genealogical, ethnographical, epidemiological, or chronic illness research)
 - **Broad Use (example #2)** - Anonymized data may be used in future academic (non-commercial) research within or beyond the general area of research of the current study.